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if(Sys.info()["user"]!="fraser"){setwd("~/Desktop/streamcontourplot/plots/"); }
else {setwd("/Users/fraser/myrepos/sdegrowth/R");}
rm(list=ls()); library("data.table") library("ggplot2") library("gridExtra")
# -----
# ----- FIGURE 1 -----
# -----
if(Sys.info()["user"]!="fraser"){setwd("~/Desktop/streamcontourplot/plots/"); }
else {setwd("/Users/fraser/myrepos/sdegrowth/R");}
load("TZtraj.RData");# provides TZtraj list load("TZchild24.RData");# provides
TZchild24.df load("SAtraj.RData");# provides SAtraj list load("SAchild24.RData");#
provides SAchild24.df
if(Sys.info()["user"]!="fraser"){setwd("~/Desktop/streamcontourplot/plots/");
} else {setwd("/Users/fraser/myrepos/sdegrowth/SASUniversityEdition/myfolders");}
fittedSDE.df<-read.csv("predcondSDE.csv",header=TRUE); # fitted values with 95% CI
SDE preds <- as.data.table(fittedSDE.df)
preds[, resid:= zwfl1 - Pred]
preds[, error:= sum(resid^2), by=subjidN]
fig1<-ggplot(data=preds, aes(x=agemnth1, y=zwfl1))+ geom_line( aes(group=subjid),
size=0.2, alpha=0.1)+ geom_smooth(colour="black",size=0.9) + coord_cartesian(ylim =
c(-2, 3)) +
#
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="TZ"])[9]],
size=0.7, colour="gold1")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="TZ"])[103]],
size=0.7,
colour="darkorchid2")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="TZ"])[1]],
size=0.7,
colour="springgreen4")+ #
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="SA"])[103]],
size=0.7, colour="royalblue1")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="SA"])[102]],
size=0.7, colour="tan1")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="SA"])[10]],
size=0.7, colour="deeppink3")+
#
scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(0,24,by=6))+
facet_wrap(~country, labeller=as_labeller(c("SA"=paste0("Venda, South
Africa", " (n=",length(SAtraj),")"),
"TZ"=paste0("Haydom, Tanzania", " (n=",length(TZtraj),")")))) + labs(x="Age
(Months)", y="Weight-for-Length z-score (ZWfL)")
print(fig1)
ggsave("Figure1ggplot.png", fig1, height=4, width = 6)
fig1bw<-ggplot(data=preds, aes(x=agemnth1, y=zwfl1))+
geom_line( aes(group=subjid), size=0.2, alpha=0.1)+
geom_smooth(colour="black",size=0.3,se=F) +
#
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="TZ"])[9]],
size=0.7, colour="grey60")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="TZ"])[103]],
size=0.7, colour="grey45")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="TZ"])[1]],
size=0.7, colour="grey30")+
#
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="SA"])[103]],
size=0.7, colour="grey60")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="SA"])[102]],
size=0.7, colour="grey45")+
geom_line(data=preds[preds$subjid==unique(preds$subjid[preds$country=="SA"])[10]],
size=0.7, colour="grey30")+ #
scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(0,24,by=6))+
facet_wrap(~country, labeller=as_labeller(c("SA"=paste0("Venda, South
Africa", " (n=",length(SAtraj),")"),
"TZ"=paste0("Haydom, Tanzania", " (n=",length(TZtraj),")")))) +
theme_classic() +
labs(x="Age (Months)", y="Weight-for-Length z-score (ZWfL)") print(fig1bw)
ggsave("Figure1ggplot_BW.png", fig1bw, height=4, width = 6)

# -----

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# ----- FIGURE 2 -----
# -----
ou.c9<-read.csv("OUfitschild9.csv",header=TRUE); ou.c103<-
read.csv("OUfitschild103.csv",header=TRUE); ou.c2<-
read.csv("OUfitschild2.csv",header=TRUE); ou.c100<-
read.csv("OUfitschild100.csv",header=TRUE);
theme_classic() +

lm.c9<-read.csv("LMfitschild9.csv",header=TRUE); lm.c103<-
read.csv("LMfitschild103.csv",header=TRUE); lm.c2<-
read.csv("LMfitschild2.csv",header=TRUE); lm.c100<-
read.csv("LMfitschild100.csv",header=TRUE);
dat.df<-read.csv("combined.csv",header=TRUE);## observed data - as used to fit
models dat <- as.data.table(dat.df)
fits <- merge(
subset(rbind(ou.c9,ou.c103,ou.c100), select=c("subjid","agects1","Pred")),
subset(rbind(lm.c9,lm.c103,lm.c100), select=c("subjid","agects1","Pred")),
by=c("subjid","agects1"),suffixes = c(".ou",".lm"))
dat.fit <- merge(dat.df, fits, by=c("subjid","agects1"), all.y=T) dat.melt <-
melt(dat.fit, id.vars=c("subjid","country","agects1"),
measure.vars = c("Pred.ou","Pred.lm","zwfl0"))
## different patients
idx <- unique(dat$subjid)[c(47, 106, 174, 233, 369, 305)]
fig2<-ggplot(data=dat.melt, aes(x=agects1*24, y=value, colour=variable,
size=variable))+
geom_line()+ geom_text(data=data.frame(subjid=unique(dat.melt$subjid),
label=c("(i)","(ii)","(iii)")),
inherit.aes = F,
aes(x=3,y=3.1,label=label))+ facet_wrap(~subjid) +
theme_classic()+ scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(0,24,by=6))+ theme(legend.position =
c(0.9,0.88),
strip.background = element_blank(),
strip.text.x = element_blank()+ guides(size="none")+
scale_size_manual(values=c("zwfl0"=0.2, "Pred.ou"=0.7,
"Pred.lm"=0.7))+ scale_colour_manual(name="Model",
values=c("zwfl0"="grey20", "Pred.ou"="dodgerblue3",
"Pred.lm"="firebrick3"), labels=c("zwfl0"="Observed",
"Pred.ou"="Ornstein-\nUhlenbeck",
"Pred.lm"="Linear\nregression"))+ labs(x="Age (Months)", y="Weight-for-Length z-
score (ZWfL)")
print(fig2);
ggsave("Figure2ggplot.png", fig2, height=4, width = 6)
fig2bw <- fig2+scale_colour_grey() ggsave("Figure2ggplot_BW.png", fig2bw, height=4,
width = 6)

# ----- FIGURE 3 -----
# -----
if(Sys.info()["user"]!="fraser"){setwd("~/Desktop/streamcontourplot/plots/");
} else {setwd("/Users/fraser/myrepos/sdegrowth/SASUniversityEdition/myfolders");}
## Read data
curve <- fread('curvepredcond.csv') sde <- fread('predcondSDE.csv')
D <- merge(
subset(curve,
select=c("subjid","agemnth0","zwfl0","zwfl1","Pred","Lower","Upper")), subset(sde,
select=c("subjid","agemnth0","zwfl0","zwfl1","Pred","Lower","Upper")),
by=c("subjid","agemnth0","zwfl0","zwfl1"),
suffixes=c(".c",".s"))
D[, country:= substr(subjid,1,2)]
## Calculate residuals from each model D[, Resid.c:= zwfl1 - Pred.c]
D[, Resid.s:= zwfl1 - Pred.s]
D[, change:= zwfl0 - zwfl1]
Z <- D[, lapply(.SD, mean), by=c("country", "agemnth0"), .SDcols=c("zwfl1",
"Pred.c", "Pred.s")]
Z <- melt(Z, id.vars=c("country","agemnth0"), measure.vars = c("zwfl1", "Pred.c",
"Pred.s"))
Z$variable <- factor(Z$variable, levels=c("zwfl1", "Pred.c", "Pred.s"),
labels=c("Observed","LMM", "SDE"))
Z$size <- ifelse(Z$variable=="Observed",0.2,0.7)
W <- D[, lapply(.SD, mean), by=c("country", "agemnth0"), .SDcols=c("zwfl1",

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"Pred.c", "Lower.c", "Upper.c",
"Pred.s", "Lower.s", "Upper.s"])

Wb <- W
W <- melt(W, id.vars=c("country","agemnth0"),
measure.vars = c("zwfl1", "Pred.c", "Lower.c", "Upper.c",
"Pred.s", "Lower.s", "Upper.s"))
W$variable <- factor(W$variable,
levels=c("zwfl1", "Pred.c", "Pred.s", "Lower.c", "Upper.c", "Lower.s", "Upper.s"),
labels=c("Observed", "LMM", "SDE", "Lower.c", "Upper.c", "Lower.s", "Upper.s"))
W$size <- ifelse(W$variable=="Observed", 0.2, 0.7)
fig3<-ggplot(data=W[variable%in%c("Observed", "LMM", "SDE")], aes(x=agemnth0,
y=value, colour=variable, linetype=variable))+
geom_ribbon(data=Wb, inherit.aes=F, aes(x=agemnth0, ymin=Lower.c, ymax=Upper.c),
alpha=0.3, fill="firebrick3")+
geom_ribbon(data=Wb, inherit.aes=F, aes(x=agemnth0, ymin=Lower.s, ymax=Upper.s),
alpha=0.4, fill="dodgerblue3")+
geom_line(aes(size=size))+
scale_size(range=c(0.4,1))+
scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(0,24,by=6))+
scale_colour_manual(values=c("Observed"="grey20", "SDE"="dodgerblue3",
"LMM"="firebrick3"))+ facet_wrap(~country, labeller=as_labeller(c("SA"="Venda,
South Africa",
"TZ"="Haydom, Tanzania")))+ theme_classic()+theme(legend.position = c(0.85,0.65))
+guides(size="none")+
labs(x="Age (months)", y="Weight-for-Length z-score (ZWFL)", colour="Model",
linetype="Model") print(fig3);
ggsave("Figure3ggplot.png", fig3, height=4, width = 6)
fig3bw<-ggplot(data=W[variable%in%c("Observed", "LMM", "SDE")], aes(x=agemnth0,
y=value, colour=variable, linetype=variable))+
geom_ribbon(data=Wb, inherit.aes=F, aes(x=agemnth0, ymin=Lower.c, ymax=Upper.c),
alpha=0.3, fill="grey70")+ geom_ribbon(data=Wb, inherit.aes=F, aes(x=agemnth0,
ymin=Lower.s, ymax=Upper.s), alpha=0.4, fill="grey50")+ geom_line(aes(size=size))+
scale_size(range=c(0.4,1))+
scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(0,24,by=6))+
scale_colour_manual(values=c("Observed"="grey20", "SDE"="grey50", "LMM"="grey90"))+
facet_wrap(~country, labeller=as_labeller(c("SA"="Venda, South Africa",
"TZ"="Haydom, Tanzania")))+ theme_classic()+theme(legend.position = c(0.85,0.65))
+guides(size="none")+
labs(x="Age (months)", y="Weight-for-Length z-score (ZWFL)", colour="Model",
linetype="Model") print(fig3bw);
ggsave("Figure3ggplot_BW.png", fig3bw, height=4, width = 6)

# -----
# ----- FIGURE 4 -----
# -----
if(Sys.info()["user"]!="fraser"){setwd("~/Desktop/streamcontourplot/plots/");
} else {setwd("/Users/fraser/myrepos/sdegrowth/SASUniversityEdition/myfolders");}
rv<-read.csv("rvsSDE.csv",header=TRUE);## random effects per child SDE model
fixedPar<-read.csv("paramsSDE.csv",header=TRUE);## fixed effects params SDE model
## create a data.frame with format {subjIDN=b1,b2,b3,b4,b5}
rv.wide <- dcast(rv, subjIDN ~ Effect, value.var="Estimate")
### global fixed parameters a1a<-fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a1a_ind"];
a1b<-fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a1b_ind"]; a2<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a2_ind"]; a3<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a3_ind"]; a4a<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a4a_ind"]; a4b<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a4b_ind"]; a5<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="a5_ind"]; sigma2a<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="sigma2a_ind"]; sigma2b<-
fixedPar$Estimate[fixedPar$Parameter=="sigma2b_ind"];
#-----
## split for initial conditions (first observation per child)
a<-split(dat$agec0, list(dat$subjIDN));
initt0=unlist(lapply(a, `[`, 1))
a<-split(dat$zwfl0, list(dat$subjIDN));
initY0=unlist(lapply(a, `[`, 1))

allinits<-data.frame(subjIDN=as.numeric(names(a)),t0=initt0,Y0=initY0);
#-----

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## for each of the 236 SDEs compute the prediction Y1 at t=0.2 given child is at
Y0=-0.5,t0=0.1
## first part - compute the density value for Y1=-0.5 at t=0.1 given observed
starting conditions at t=0.035 ## only work with TZ data
SAinits<-allinits[SA.subjidN,];## id is same as row number
SArv<-rv.wide[SA.subjidN,];
TZinits<-allinits[TZ.subjidN,];## id is same as row number TZrv<-
rv.wide[TZ.subjidN,];
#-----
## function to calculate fitted SDE prediction given parameters and starting
conditions
sdeMoments<-function(time0,# start time
Y0,# start value
country2,# country = 0=SA, 1=TZ
timevec,# time points to evaluate at after time0
a1a.fx,a1b.fx,a2.fx,a3.fx,a4a.fx,a4b.fx,a5.fx, #fixed effect parameters
sigma2a.fx,sigma2b.fx, # fixed effect parameters
b1,b2,b3,b4, # random effect parameters
Yt=NULL# compute the density value under the current model for Y(timevec|Y0,t0)
){
if(!is.null(Yt)){## want to compute density to check only single future time point
passed
if(length(timevec)!=1){stop("for density value estimation timevec must be single
time point")}}
}
a1=a1a.fx+a1b.fx*country2+b1;
a2=a2.fx+b2;
a3=a3.fx+b3;
a4=a4a.fx+a4b.fx*country2;
a5=a5.fx;
sigma2=sigma2a.fx+sigma2b.fx*country2+b4;

loc.mean<-((1/(a1**4))*exp(-a1*time0)*(6*a5*(exp(a1*timevec) - exp(a1*time0)) +
2*a1*(a4*exp(a1*timevec) - a4*exp(a1*time0) - 3*a5*exp(a1*time0)*timevec +
3*a5*exp(a1*timevec)*time0) +
a1**2*(a3*(exp(a1*timevec) - exp(a1*time0)) - 2*a4*exp(a1*time0)*timevec -
3*a5*exp(a1*time0)*timevec**2 + 2*a4*exp(a1*timevec)*time0 +
3*a5*exp(a1*timevec)*time0**2) +
a1**3*(a2*(exp(a1*timevec) - exp(a1*time0)) - a3*exp(a1*time0)*timevec -
a4*exp(a1*time0)*timevec**2 - a5*exp(a1*time0)*timevec**3 +
a3*exp(a1*timevec)*time0 +
a4*exp(a1*timevec)*time0**2 + a5*exp(a1*timevec)*time0**3) +
a1**4*exp(a1*timevec)*Y0);

loc.sd<-sqrt(((1.0+exp(2*a1*(timevec-time0)))*sigma2)/(2*a1));

if(is.null(Yt)){## if Yt is null then compute mean trajectory
return(list(Y0=Y0,t0=time0,mean=loc.mean,sd=loc.sd,times=timevec))
} else {## Yt is valid so compute single density value at Y(timevec|Y0,t0)
return(list(Y0=Y0,t0=time0,t1=timevec,
density=dnorm(Yt,mean=loc.mean,sd=loc.sd));
}
}

#-----
### - MAIN manuscript version - weights are based on likelihood condition on
starting point at the earliest possible age of the each child
##SA
timestep=0.05
nfolds <- 10
P <- data.frame(
start=NULL, startT=NULL, subjN=NULL,
time0 = NULL, Y0 = NULL,country2 = NULL,
timevec = NULL,Y1 = NULL)
for(start in seq(-3, 3, by=0.5)){
for(startT in c(0.1,0.2,0.35, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9)){
for(i in 1:nrow(SAinits)){

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timevec = seq(startT, (1-timestep), by=timestep)
for(k in 1:length(timevec)){
  if(k==1){
    t0<-startT #SAinits$t0[i];
    Y0<-start #SAinits$Y0[i];
    t1 <- timevec[k]+timestep
  } else{
    t0 <- P[nrow(P), "t1"]
    Y0 <- P[nrow(P), "Y1"]
    t1 <- timevec[k]+timestep
  }
  Beta_mean<-sdeMoments(time0=t0,
  Y0=Y0,
  country2=1,
  timevec=t1,
  a1a.fx=a1a,a1b.fx=a1b,a2.fx=a2,a3.fx=a3,a4a.fx=a4a,a4b.fx=a4b,a5.fx=a5,
  sigma2a.fx=sigma2a,sigma2b.fx=sigma2b,
  b1=SArv$b1[i],b2=SArv$b2[i],b3=SArv$b3[i],b4=SArv$b4[i],
  Yt=NULL)$mean;#
  Beta_density<-sdeMoments(time0=t0,
  Y0=Y0,
  country2=1,
  timevec=t1,
  a1a.fx=a1a,a1b.fx=a1b,a2.fx=a2,a3.fx=a3,a4a.fx=a4a,a4b.fx=a4b,a5.fx=a5,
  sigma2a.fx=sigma2a,sigma2b.fx=sigma2b,
  b1=SArv$b1[i],b2=SArv$b2[i],b3=SArv$b3[i],b4=SArv$b4[i],
  Yt=Beta_mean)$density;#
  P <- rbind(P,
  data.frame(
  start=start,
  startT=startT,
  subjN=i,
  time0 = t0,
  Y0 = Y0,
  country2=1,
  t1 = t1,
  Y1 = Beta_mean,
  Y1density = Beta_density
  ))
}# loop time step
}# loop parameters
}# loop starting ZWFL
}# loop starting time

#-----
##TZ
timestep=0.05
nfolds <- 10
## Add to SA data.frame
# P <- data.frame(
# start=NULL, startT=NULL, subjN=NULL,
# time0 = NULL, Y0 = NULL,country2 = NULL,
# timevec = NULL,Y1 = NULL)
for(start in seq(-3, 3, by=0.5)){
  for(startT in c(0.1,0.2,0.35, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9)){
    for(i in 1:nrow(TZinits)){
      timevec = seq(startT, (1-timestep), by=timestep)
      for(k in 1:length(timevec)){
        if(k==1){
          t0<-startT #TZinits$t0[i];
          Y0<-start #TZinits$Y0[i];
          t1 <- timevec[k]+timestep
        } else{
          t0 <- P[nrow(P), "t1"]
          Y0 <- P[nrow(P), "Y1"]
          t1 <- timevec[k]+timestep
        }
        Beta_mean<-sdeMoments(time0=t0,
        Y0=Y0,
        country2=0,
        timevec=t1,

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a1a.fx=a1a,a1b.fx=a1b,a2.fx=a2,a3.fx=a3,a4a.fx=a4a,a4b.fx=a4b,a5.fx=a5,
sigma2a.fx=sigma2a,sigma2b.fx=sigma2b,
b1=TZrv$b1[i],b2=TZrv$b2[i],b3=TZrv$b3[i],b4=TZrv$b4[i],
Yt=NULL)$mean;#
Beta_density<-sdeMoments(time0=t0,
Y0=Y0,
country2=0,
timevec=t1,
a1a.fx=a1a,a1b.fx=a1b,a2.fx=a2,a3.fx=a3,a4a.fx=a4a,a4b.fx=a4b,a5.fx=a5,
sigma2a.fx=sigma2a,sigma2b.fx=sigma2b,
b1=TZrv$b1[i],b2=TZrv$b2[i],b3=TZrv$b3[i],b4=TZrv$b4[i],
Yt=Beta_mean)$density;#
P <- rbind(P,
data.frame(
start=start,
startT=startT,
subjN=i,
time0 = t0,
Y0 = Y0,
country2=0,
t1 = t1,
Y1 = Beta_mean,
Y1density = Beta_density
))
}# loop time step
}# loop parameters
}# loop starting ZWFL
}# loop starting time

#-----
## N folds validation
## for each starting condition (age and zwfl), take the best fit
## (highest density) from each of 10 random subgroups
P$model <- interaction(P$start, P$startT, P$country2)
Q <- NULL
g=0
for(i in unique(P$model)){
p <- as.data.table(subset(P, model==i))# select the starting conditions
id <- unique(P$subjN) # identify the initial parameters
k <- sample(1:10, length(id),replace=T) #assign into 10 groups
p[, grp:=k[subjN]]

for(j in 1:10){
tmp <- subset(p, grp==j)
tmp <- subset(tmp, Y1density==max(tmp$Y1density))
g=g+1
tmp[, idx:= g]
Q <- rbind(Q,tmp)
}
}

#-----
# plot
fig4bw <- ggplot(data=Q,
aes(x=t1, y=Y1, group=idx))+
geom_line(alpha=0.1)+
geom_rug(data=preds[agemnth1==24, list(zwfl1 = zwfl1),
by="subjid"],aes(y=zwfl1),inherit.aes=F, sides="r",alpha=0.2,
length = unit(0.015, "npc"))+
geom_rug(data=preds[agemnth0==0, list(zwfl0 = zwfl0),
by="subjid"],aes(y=zwfl0),inherit.aes=F, sides="l",alpha=0.2,
length = unit(0.015, "npc"))+
facet_wrap(~country2,labeller=as_labeller(c("0"="SAV","1"="TZH")))
+guides(colour="none")+
theme_classic()+ theme(title=element_text(size=rel(0.8)))+
labs(x="Age", y="ZWfL",colour="Starting\nZWfL",title="Predicted ZWfL given
different starting ZwFL (colour)\nand age")
ggsave("Fig4_BW.png", fig4bw, height=4, width = 6)

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